

A prescriptive analysis tool for improving manufacturing processes

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Abstract Recently more digital twins have been developed and used in the manufacturing industry. Some are based on detailed models of a particular machine/process oriented to monitoring, but others can represent a full manufacturing plant for production planning. These models involve a lot of parameters, and it is not easy to evaluate the effect of their change in the manufactured product or how they are correlated among them. This paper presents a prescriptive analysis tool that allows testing and ranking multiple scenarios using a previously generated digital twin. This is thus, a simulation, evaluation, and prescription tool. It uses a set of available models, allowing the selection of the parameters and defining the scenarios to be simulated, as well as the evaluation configuration. The tool performs exhaustive simulations making initially all possible combinations of the parameters selected and obtaining the simulation results for each of them. After this the evaluation is performed over some of the outputs of the model, leading to a ranking of all the simulations. The prescription obtained can be later used to configure a machine or to change some production parameters to optimize the system.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the manufacturing industry is evolving towards Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing. However, being data the central and common theme in both Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing, the increasing complexity of manufacturing systems and the huge amount of raw data that is being recorded non-stop has

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resulted in a challenging evolution (Matyas *et al.*, 2017). To deal with those issues companies have switched to more complex and varied analysis tools: descriptive, predictive, detective, cognitive and prescriptive analysis tools specifically (Menezes *et al.*, 2019). However, those advanced analysis tools do not only require a heavy computational load, but also a large database with operating data in both correct and incorrect conditions (such as failure or wear). In addition, having a large database can result in having difficulties to correlate data and so, to get the whole picture of the factory floor (Lepenioti *et al.*, 2020).

Advanced analysis tools are usually data-based (Chae *et al.*, 2014; Matyas *et al.*, 2017), i.e., the analysis is carried out by means of a model generated with the data of the sensors of a machine. The model replaces the real machine or process as its digital twin (DT), a virtual representation of a physical system and its environment which is updated through the information exchange between the physic and virtual systems (Semeraro *et al.*, 2021). In addition to the mentioned data-based DTs, models can also be physic-based: a model generated from the equations that define the laws of nature (Erikstad, 2017).

The use of DTs reduces costs and risk, improves reliability and resilience and supports decision making (VanDerHorn and Mahadevan, 2021). What is more, DTs are not limited to a certain field or process, they can be used to model anything, from a particular machine or process (tool wear degradation for instance) to the planning or production of a manufacturing plant. However, the challenge with DTs is that even the simplest DT has a significant number of internal parameters to tune. The effect of these parameters in the behavior of the model is difficult to predict, that is, it is difficult to know how a slight variation of a parameter could change the behavior of the whole process. This information is critical to optimize the system or to predict the effect of material wear, vibration or other disturbances in the behavior model. That is why prescriptive analysis tools are so important. These analysis tools find or prescribe the best mode, route or manner (outputs) to operate a system based on given data and models (inputs) (Menezes *et al.*, 2019).

Thus, the prescriptive analysis (PA) tool presented in this paper is a simulation, optimization and prescription tool that allows the prescription of both physics- and data-based models through a user-friendly interface. The prescription is carried out by evaluating different sets of system parameters on a preestablished target function. Once the evaluation of all the alternatives is done, the variations are ranked and listed from the most to the less scored ones. The system variations are either variations of the configurations of a model or variations of the inputs of a model. Working with variations of a model allows to analyze the behavior of the model in different working conditions.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows; in section 2 the prescription process is described in detail; and the conclusions are presented in section 3.

2 Prescriptive Analysis Tool

The whole process of prescription is represented in Figure 1. The prescription process can be divided in four different phases: the model configuration phase (blue dotted square), the evaluation configuration phase (green dashed square), the actual prescription process (yellow dot-dashed square) and the results visualization phase (purple double dot-dashed square). The PA tool requires a model library, from which the model to carry out the simulations is selected, and optionally can use a time series database as input data for the simulations.

Figure 1: Prescription process diagram

The prescription process starts with the selection of a model. The model can be physics- or data-based. It should be highlighted that in the former case the models are supported by the FMI standard (*Functional Mock-up Interface*). Thus, any selected physics-based model contains state variables, input and output variables, constants and parameters. Once the model is selected, the user has to define the map of values to explore, that is, the values of the internal parameters of the model to carry out simulations with. For each parameter to be analyzed the user has to define the minimum, maximum and step value of the parameter, with which a vector is defined. The vector contains all the values between the defined minimum and maximum values, considering the defined step. This vector defines the map of values, one vector for each parameter to be analyzed. By combining the values of the different vectors with each other the different simulation scenarios are defined. As an example: if 3 parameters were considered to be analyzed, and 4, 5 and 8 values are defined for each of them, respectively, the map of scenarios would be $4 * 5 * 8 = 160$ long, what means that the PA tool would carry out 160 simulations. In other words, each simulation corresponds to a model configuration (a

specific line of the map of scenarios), and each model configuration is a potential prescription of an optimization function.

The second phase of the PA is the evaluation configuration phase. In order to configure the evaluation, two elements need to be defined: some metrics to be calculated using the outputs of the simulations, and a function to evaluate the configured scenarios using the metrics. On the one hand, a library of metrics is available, which contains some basic (e.g., mean, mode, root-mean-square) and complex features. On the other hand, an optimization function is defined, which is composed of the mentioned metrics. In other words, every optimization function minimizes or maximizes a mathematical expression composed of a series of metrics. An evaluation library is available, containing predefined optimization functions, but the user can add custom optimization functions as well. At least one evaluation function must be configured to perform the prescription.

In the third phase the PA uses the previously configured data to carry out the simulation, evaluation and prescription of the model. As shown in Figure 1, the model configuration is required to carry out the simulations, and the simulations results and the evaluation configuration is required to carry out the evaluation and prescription. The evaluation process can include more than one optimization function and it is applied once for every simulation. Therefore, the result of the evaluation process is a table of $n \times m$, where n is the number of simulations, and m the number of selected optimization functions, and every cell's value is the output of a specific optimization functions for a specific simulation.

The last phase of the prescription process is the visualization of the results in which the simulations' outputs and the prescription are displayed. The simulations' outputs visualizer contains a two-level filtering system with which the user can easily analyze the results in batches. As for the prescription visualizer, the evaluation results are displayed through some elements. The first element displays the previously mentioned evaluation results table which can be sorted according to a specific optimization function, and so, simulations can be ranked in terms of the selected function. The second element is a dynamic table which displays the prescription (the model configuration) of the selected line in the evaluation results table. The third and last element is a bar graph which shows the evaluation result of all the simulations.

The whole prescription process, depicted in Figure 1 and explained in detail previously, is carried out using a user-friendly web interface, designed and developed for non-expert users in modelling and prescription techniques, allowing the use of this tool by different roles in manufacturing companies. Figure 2 shows the first phase of the PA tool: the model selection and configuration.

Figure 2. View of the PA tool

3 Conclusions

The PA tool presented in this paper is a configurable and user-friendly software that allows the user to simulate manufacturing scenarios, evaluate the results and prescribe optimal configurations using physics-based and data-driven models. The user selects a model and the range of values of the parameters of that model, creating a map of scenarios. Moreover, the evaluation criterion is defined based on some features and evaluation functions. The different scenarios are then simulated and evaluated according to the selected evaluation functions. Then, the evaluation results are used to rank the scenarios, obtaining a prescription for the system in terms of optimum configurations. These results can be used to configure a machine or to change some production parameters to optimize a manufacturing line or the results of a process. This tool suggests system configurations, but it does not have any connection to the manufacturing line or process being prescribed. Thus, further work could be related to close the loop and reconfigure the system being analyzed, bearing in mind that any reconfiguration needs to be approved by skilled personnel and, therefore, the proposed functionality would not be automatically executed.

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